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CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021105584

The Commissioner of Patents has granted the above patent on 17 November 2021, and certifies that the below particulars have been registered in the Register of Patents.

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Title of invention:

Fabrication and Evaluation of Gastro Retentive Tablet of Trandolapril in Treatment of Essential Hypertension

Name of inventor(s):

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Term of Patent:

Eight years from 16 August 2021

NOTE: This Innovation Patent cannot be enforced unless and until it has been examined by the Commissioner of Patents and a Certificate of Examination has been issued. See sections 120(1A) and 129A of the Patents Act 1990, set out on the reverse of this document.

Dated this 17th day of November 2021

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

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